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Research Article

**FORMULATION, DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF
EXTENDED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS OF GLIPIZIDE****M.Sreenivas Varma*, T.Mallika, S.Spandana**

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Abstract:

Glipizide is used for treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. It is IInd generation sulfonylurea derivative. It is BCS class 2 drug and has a half life of 2-4 hours. The usual dosage is 2.5, 5 and 10 mg twice or thrice a day. To reduce the frequency of administration and to improve the patient compliance, a once daily extended release formulation of Glipizide is desirable. Hence selection of rate controlling excipient is necessary to achieve a constant in vivo input of drug. Hence in the present work an attempt has been made to develop extended release matrix tablets of Glipizide using hydrophilic matrix materials such as hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose and Ethyl cellulose. The most commonly used method of modulating the drug release is to include it in a matrix system. Diffusion controlled polymeric matrix systems have been widely used as drug delivery systems owing to their flexibility to obtain a desirable drug release profile, cost effectiveness and broad regulatory acceptance.

Keywords: *Glipizide, Sulfonylurea derivative, Extended release matrix tablets, Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose, Ethyl Cellulose.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disorder characterized by chronic hyper-glycemia with disturbances of carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action or both. Hyperglycemia or raised blood sugar is a common effect of uncontrolled diabetes and over time leads to serious damage to many of the body's systems, especially the nerves and blood vessels. There are mainly three types of diabetes mellitus. They are Type 1 diabetes (Insulin dependent DM), Type 2 diabetes (Non-insulin DM), Gestational diabetes.

Need for Formulating Extended Release Matrix

Tablets: The design of effective drug delivery systems has recently become an integral part of the development of new medicines. The goal is to provide a therapeutic quantity of medicine(s) to the proper site in the body in order to achieve the desired effect and maintain such effect for the entire period of treatment. Hence research continuously keeps on searching for ways to deliver drugs over an extended period of time, with a well-controlled release profile.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials: Glipizide (Cadila Pharmaceuticals), Ethyl Cellulose (Colorcon), HPMC K4 M (Colorcon), Dicalcium Phosphate (Remedy Labs), Magnesium Stearate (Ferro Ltd.), Talc (Micro Filler).

DRUG IDENTIFICATION TESTS:

Organoleptic Properties: The Organoleptic properties of drug that is colour, odour and taste were tested and were compared with literature.

Melting Point Determination: Capillary tube of sufficient length was taken and its one end was sealed by heating over a flame. Sufficient amount of drug was filled and was placed in a melting point apparatus. The capillary tube was observed for melting of drug.

Solubility Studies: The excess amount of drug was added to 30ml of various media in different 50 ml volumetric flask. The volume was made up to the mark and subjected to shaking on a shaker for 24 hours. After 24 hours the solution were filtered through whatmann filter paper. The amount of drug in filtrate was calculated as mg of Glipizide that goes into per ml of solvent or media by using UV spectrometer. Solubility was carried out at room temperature.

FTIR Spectrum of Glipizide: The pure drug was mixed with IR grade potassium bromide in a ratio of (1:100) and pellets were prepared by applying 10

metric ton of pressure in hydrophilic press. The pellets were then scanned over range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} in FTIR instrument (8400 S Shimadzu). FTIR spectrum of Glipizide was compared with the reference spectra.

Construction of Calibration Curve of Glipizide:

Preparation of pH 7.4 Buffer Solution: 2.38 gm of disodium hydrogen phosphate, 0.19 gm of Potassium Dihydrogen phosphate and 8gm of NaCl was dissolved in sufficient water to produce 1000 ml. pH is adjusted if necessary.

Determination of λ_{max} by UV Spectroscopy: 100 mg of Glipizide was weighed and transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask. Drug was dissolved in 50 ml of phosphate buffer having pH 7.4 and shaken manually for 10 min. The volume was made up to the mark with same media and the final concentration obtained was 1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. From this solution of 1ml was pipetted out and diluted up to 100 ml to obtain a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Scanned the solution between 200 nm to 400 nm wavelengths in U.V.-Visible Spectrophotometer.

Preparation of Stock Solution and Standard Solution:

Stock solution: 100 mg of Glipizide was dissolved in 100 ml of phosphate buffer having pH 7.4 to prepare a stock solution (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$).

Standard solutions: Solution of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were prepared by taking 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3.0 ml of stock solutions in 100ml volumetric flasks and diluting them with phosphate buffer pH 7.4 up to mark. The ultraviolet absorbance of the solutions was measured at 275 nm using UV spectrophotometer.

CHARACTERIZATION OF DRUG:

Bulk Density: Weigh accurately 10 gm of drug which was previously passed through 40 # sieve and transferred into 100 ml measuring cylinder. Volume occupied by the drug was noted without disturbing the cylinder and bulk density was calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{\text{Weight of drug}}{\text{Volume of packed}}$$

Tapped Density: Weight accurately 10 gm of drug and placed into 100 ml measuring cylinder. The measuring cylinder subjected to 500 taps and volume is measured and recorded. Tapping is continued for 750 taps and volume is again recorded, it should not vary by more than 2%. If not succeed than tap for

1250 taps. Tap density was calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{Tap density} = \frac{\text{Mass of bulk drug}}{\text{Volume of bulk drug on tapping}}$$

Carr's Index (Compressibility index):

Compressibility is indirectly related to the relative flow rate, cohesiveness and particle Size distribution of the powder. Compressibility of the powder was determined using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Compressibility} = \frac{\text{Tap density} - \text{Bulk density}}{\text{Bulk density}} \times 100$$

Hausner's Ratio: Hausner's ratio of the powder was determined using the following formula:

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped density}}{\text{Bulk density}}$$

Angle of Repose: The angle of repose gives an indication of the flow ability of the substance. Funnel was adjusted in such a way that the stem of the funnel lies 5 cm above the horizontal surface. The powder was allowed to flow from the funnel under the gravitational force till the tip of the pile just touched the tip of the funnel, so the height of the pile was taken as 2 cm. The diameter of the pile was determined by drawing a boundary along the circumference of the pile and taking the average of six diameters. These values of height and diameter were then substituted in the following equation.

$$\text{Angle of repose } (\theta) = \tan^{-1}(h/r)$$

Where, h is height of the pile and r is the radius of the pile

Drug - Excipients Compatibility Study:

Compatibility study was performed by keeping the blend of the drug substance with different excipients

at accelerated condition of 40°C / 75 % RH and 60°C. Samples were kept in sealed vials and checked for any physical change and chemical change after storing for an interval of two weeks and four weeks. After checking excipients and API compatibility, finally compatible excipients were selected for final formulation.

Table No: 1 Ratio of Glipizide and Excipient for Compatibility Study

S. No	Ingredient	Drug : Excipient
1	Glipizide	API Only
2	Glipizide + EC	1:0.1
3	Glipizide + HPMC K4 M	1:1
5	Glipizide + DCP	1:1
6	Glipizide + Mg. Stearate	1:0.5
7	Glipizide + Talc	1:0.5

Particle Size Determination: Accurately weighed 50 gm of dried granules was accurately weighed and transferred to sieve shaker. Sieve shaker was kept at power 10 for 5 min. Sieve of different mesh size used for analysis and calculate the amount of granules that retain on each the sieve.

FORMULATION OF EXTENDED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS:

Matrix formulation was designed for Glipizide using Hydroxy Propyl Methylcellulose (HPMC) and Ethyl Cellulose in combination. Cellulosic polymers are well known matrix forming agents, however they suffer from burst release in the initial phase of dissolution, which is controlled by polymers in this system.

Table No: 2 Formula of Glipizide Extended Release Tablets

Ingredients(mg/tablet)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
Glipizide	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Ethyl Cellulose	10	15	20	10	15	20	25
HPMC	-	-	-	10	10	10	10
Dicalcium Phosphate	172	167	162	162	157	152	147
Talc	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Magnesium Stearate	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Total Weight(mg)	200						

Evaluation of Glipizide Matrix Tablets:

Description: The physical description of dosage form like colour and shape were checked carefully to get idea regarding design parameters of dosage form.

Weight Variation: Every individual tablet in a batch should be in uniform weight. Twenty tablets were randomly selected from prepared batch and accurately weighed using an electronic balance. The results were within the Standard Pharmacopoeial limits.

Table No: 3 Limits of Tablet Weight Variation

Average Weight of Tablet (mg)	% Difference
130 or less	10
From 130 to 324	7.5
More than 324	5

Thickness: The thicknesses of the tablets were determined by Vernier calipers.

Hardness: The hardness of the tablets was determined by hardness tester.

Friability: The friability of the tablets was measured in a Roche friabilator. Tablets of a known weight (W_0) or sample of 10 tablets are kept in a friabilator for a fixed time (100 revolutions) and weighed (W) again. Percentage friability was calculated from the loss in weight as given in equation as below. The weight loss should not be more than 1 % w/w with no breakage of any tablet.

$$\% \text{ Friability} = \frac{W_0 - W}{W_0} \times 100$$

Assay of Prepared Tablet: Twenty tablets were weighed and crushed to obtain a fine powder. An accurately weighted sample equivalent to 40 mg of Glipizide (2.4 gm tablet powder) was taken in a stoppered volumetric flask (100 ml); 50ml of phosphate buffer pH7.4 was added and shaken manually for 5 min. The volume was made up to the mark with the same solvent and solution was filtered through whatmann filter paper (No 41). From this solution 1 ml taken and further diluted with phosphate buffer of pH7.4 up to 20 ml. Absorbance were measured at 275 nm against blank. The concentrations of drugs in solution were calculated by using calibration curve.

In vitro Dissolution Study: *In-vitro* release study of tablets was done using USP27 dissolution apparatus II (Paddle). Vessel was filled with 900 ml Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and temperature was maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C. Paddle was revolved at 50 rpm speed. 5ml of sample was withdrawn after every hour and replaced with 5ml of fresh dissolution medium respectively to maintain sink condition. Samples were analyzed using UV spectrometer for drug content at 275 nm.

Drug Release Kinetics: The mathematical models are used to evaluate the kinetics and mechanism of drug release from the tablet. The model that gives high 'r' (correlation coefficient) value is considered as the best fit of the release data. Mathematical models are Zero order release model, First order release model, Higuchi release model, Korsmeyer-

Peppas release model

1. Zero Order Release Model: The equation for zero order is

$$Q_t = Q_0 + K_0 t$$

Where, Q_0 = Initial amount of drug

Q_t = Cumulative amount of drug release at the 't' time

K_0 = Zero-order release constant

t = time in hours

It describes the systems where the drug release rate is independent of its concentration of the dissolved substance.

2. First Order Release Model: The equation for first order is

$$\text{Log } Q_t = \text{Log } Q_0 + Kt / 2.303$$

Where, Q_0 = Initial amount of drug

Q_t = Cumulative amount of drug release at the 't' time

K = First-order release constant

Here, the drug release rate depend on its concentration.

3. Higuchi Release Model:

$$Q = K_H t^{1/2}$$

Where, Q = Cumulative amount of drug release at the 't' time

K_H = Higuchi constant

The Higuchi equation suggest that the drug release by diffusion.

4. Korsmeyer - Peppas Release Model:

$$F = (M_t / M) = K_m t^n$$

Where, F = Fraction of drug release at time 't'

M_t = Amount of drug release at time 't'

M = Total amount of drug in dosage form

K_m = Kinetic constant

n = diffusion or release exponent

The 'n' is estimated from linear regression of $\log (M_t / M) / \log t$. If $n=0.45$ indicate fickian diffusion. If $0.45 < n < 0.89$ indicates anomalous diffusion or non-fickian diffusion. If $n=0.89$ and above indicate case 2 relaxation or super case transport-2. Anomalous diffusion or non-fickian diffusion refers to combination of both diffusion and erosion controlled rate release. Case-2 relaxation or super case transport-2 refers to the erosion of the polymeric chain.

Stability Study: The purpose of stability testing is to provide evidence on how the quality, efficacy and safety of a drug substance or drug product varies with time the time under the influence of a variety of environmental factors such as temperature, humidity and light and to establish a retest period for the drug substance or a shelf life for the drug product and recommended storage conditions. In general,

“significant change” for a drug product is defined as

1. A 5% change in assay from its initial value; or failure to meet the acceptance criteria for potency when using biological or immunological procedures
2. Any degradation product's exceeding its acceptance criterion
3. Failure to meet the acceptance criteria for appearance, physical attributes, and functionality test (e.g., color, phase separation, re-suspendibility, caking, hardness, dose delivery per actuation); however, some changes in physical attributes (e.g., softening of suppositories, melting of creams) may be expected under accelerated conditions and, as appropriate for the dosage form
4. Failure to meet the acceptance criterion for pH
5. Failure to meet the acceptance criteria for dissolution for 12 dosage units.

Methodology: The optimized batch of the Glipizide was subjected to accelerated studies at the condition of 40°C / 75%RH in the stability chamber. 30 tablets were packed in the HDPE container with cotton. The samples were withdrawn at the time interval of 1, 2, and 3 months and tested for the physical appearance, hardness, thickness, friability, LOD, % assay and dissolution profile. All above test results were compared to Initial data as well as standard stability requirements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Glipizide is practically insoluble in acidic media (0.01N HCl, 0.1N HCl, Acetate Buffer pH 4.5) and water. However it is soluble in alkaline media (Phosphate Buffer pH 6.8 & Phosphate pH 7.4).

Organoleptic Characteristics of Glipizide:

Table No: 4 Organoleptic Characteristics

Properties	Glipizide
Description	Crystalline
Taste	Bitter
Odour	Odorless
Colour	White to off white

Melting Point Determination: Melting point of drug was found to be ranged between 208°C to 210°C.

Solubility Studies:

Table No: 5 Solubility Profile of Glipizide

Media	Solubility (mg/ml)	Solubility in 250ml Solvent (mg)
	(Mean±SD)	(Mean±SD)
0.01N HCl	0.005±0.0001	1.25±0.0005
0.1N HCl	0.002±0.0002	0.5±0.0010
Acetate Buffer pH 4.5	0.002±0.0003	0.5±0.0015
Phosphate Buffer pH 6.8	0.045±0.0014	11.25±0.070
Purified Water	0.002±0.0001	0.5±0.0005
Phosphate Buffer pH 7.4	0.053±0.0021	13.25±0.0105

FTIR Spectrum of Glipizide: The IR spectrum of Glipizide is shown in Figure and the following characteristic bands were observed 1689 (- C=O, Amide), 1651 (- C=O, Urea), 1528 (Ar- CH, stretching), 1433 (Ar-CH, bending), and 1333 and 1159 cm⁻¹ (- SO₂NH). The IR spectrum of Glipizide showed the presence of characteristic bands of Glipizide.

Table No: 6 FTIR Spectrum of Glipizide Standard and Glipizide Sample

S.No	Standard spectra (cm ⁻¹)	Sample spectra (cm ⁻¹)	Type of vibrations
1	1690	1689	-C=O(Amide) stretching
2	1650	1651	-C=O(Urea) stretching
3	1528	1528	Ar-CH, stretching
4	1433	1433	Ar-CH, Bending
5	1159	1159&1333	-SO ₂ NH stretching

Fig No: 1 FTIR Spectrum of Glipizide

Calibration Curve of Glipizide:**Determination of λ_{max} by UV Spectroscopy:**

The solution of Glipizide was found to exhibit maximum absorption at 275 nm after scanning on the spectrophotometer between 200 nm to 400 nm wavelengths.

Table No: 7 Absorbance of Glipizide in Phosphate buffer pH 7.4

S. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance* AM \pm SD
1.	0	0 \pm 0.000
2.	2	0.048 \pm 0.0015
3.	4	0.094 \pm 0.0017
4.	6	0.141 \pm 0.0025
5.	8	0.187 \pm 0.0026
6.	10	0.233 \pm 0.0025

Fig No: 3 Calibration curve of Glipizide in Phosphate Buffer pH 7.4

The calibration curve and the data obtained by the method described in methodology section are given in Table No:7 and Figure no:3. The data had correlation coefficient of 0.999 and the equation of regressed line depicted as below:

$$y = 0.0234x + 0.0031$$

Drug-Excipient Compatibility Studies:

Table 8: Compatibility Study Profile for Glipizide and Excipients

S.No	Ingredient	Initial		40°C/75%RH (Sealed Vials)				60°C (Sealed Vials)			
				15 days		30 days		15 days		30 days	
		HUK	Total RS	HUK	Total RS	HUK	Total RS	HUK	Total RS	HUK	Total RS
(% W/W)											
1.	Glipizide	ND	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.04	0.12	0.04	0.08	0.08	0.17
2.	Glipizide + Ethyl Cellulose	0.04	0.09	0.04	0.12	0.07	0.22	0.15	0.57	0.22	0.74
3.	Glipizide + HPMC	0.01	0.04	0.02	0.08	0.04	0.13	0.08	0.33	0.12	0.89
4.	Glipizide + Di Calcium Phosphate	ND	0.01	ND	0.05	0.02	0.11	0.05	0.28	0.09	0.54
5.	Glipizide + Talc	0.03	0.07	0.04	0.11	0.08	0.32	0.07	0.54	0.22	0.89
6.	Glipizide + Mg. Stearate	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.08	0.07	0.27	0.09	0.58	0.17	0.85

Note: HUK – Highest Unknown Impurity, ND – Not Detected, RS – Related Substance

Drug-excipient compatibility study was carried out as outlined in the experimental part. All drug excipient blends were evaluated for related substances using HPLC technique. Based on HPLC results, The total impurities of all combination of drug with excipients was less than 1.0% w/w so, it was concluded that there were no interaction between them all the excipients compatible with Glipizide at 40°C/75%RH and 60°C for a period of 30 days.

Evaluation of Blend:

As defined in experimental section, the value of Compressibility index and Angle of repose ranges from 11 to 15 and < 30 have good flow character. From the above result, it can be seen that compressibility index and Angle of repose of granules ranged from 11.32±0.049 to 15.10±0.051 and 26 ±0.3 to 29 ±0.4 indicated good flow characteristic. Also, it can be seen that LOD is suitable for compression.

Table 9: Physical Properties of Granules (n±3)

Batches	Bulkdensity (g/mL)	Tapped density(g/mL)	%Carr's Index	Hausner's Ratio	Angle of Repose(θ)	%LOD
F1	0.46±0.016	0.53±0.016	13.21±0.058	1.15±0.01	28±.02	1.78
F2	0.47±0.012	0.54±0.025	12.97±0.046	1.49±0.02	27.5±0.5	1.83
F3	0.44±0.013	0.51±0.026	13.72±0.046	1.16±0.01	28±0.3	1.80
F4	0.47±0.016	0.53±0.018	11.32±0.049	1.13±0.01	26±0.3	1.69
F5	0.46±0.025	0.52±0.014	11.54±0.047	1.13±0.02	29±0.4	1.46
F6	0.47±0.019	0.55±0.017	14.54±0.047	1.17±0.01	27±0.04	1.81
F7	0.45±0.015	0.50±0.025	12.8±0.057	1.14±0.01	26±0.03	1.87

Particle size Analysis: As observed the blend retention above #80 is more than 60 % in all the case hence the entire blends are suitable for compression without flow issues.

Table 10: Sieve Analysis of Granules

Sieve no.	Percentage Weight Retain of Granules						
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
#20	11	12	10	11	14	9	12
#40	17	16	19	17	17	16	18
#60	35	37	33	38	33	40	34
#80	20	18	22	18	19	19	20
#100	12	10	12	9	11	10	9
Below # 100	5	7	4	7	6	6	7

Tablet Evaluation: It can be seen from the results. All the formulated tablets passed weight variation test as the % weight variation was within the Standard Pharmacopoeial limits of $\pm 5\%$ of the weight. The weights of all the tablets were found to be uniform with low standard deviation values. The hardness of tablets for F1 and F7 ranged between 7.5 ± 0.5 to $8.6 \pm 0.4 \text{ kg/cm}^2$. This ensures good handling characteristics for all batches. The Percentage

friability was less than 1% in all the formulations ensuring that the tablets were mechanically stable. The percentage of drug content for all batches was found to be between 97.92% and 99.93% of Glipizide, it complies with official specifications. Tablets mean thickness were uniform in all formulations and were found to be in the range of $2.93 \pm 0.05 \text{ mm}$ to $2.97 \pm 0.05 \text{ mm}$.

Table 11: Physical properties of tablets

Batch no.	Avg. wt. of tablet (mg)\$	Thickness (mm)#	Hardness (Kg/cm^2)*	Friability (%)*	% Assay*
F1	201 \pm 4	2.93 \pm 0.06	8.0 \pm 0.5	0.27 \pm 0.03	99.68 \pm 0.65
F2	198 \pm 3	2.97 \pm 0.05	8.5 \pm 0.5	0.27 \pm 0.02	99.78 \pm 0.64
F3	198 \pm 4	2.95 \pm 0.06	8.2 \pm 0.5	0.28 \pm 0.01	97.92 \pm 0.25
F4	199 \pm 2	2.94 \pm 0.05	7.8 \pm 0.6	0.25 \pm 0.03	98.40 \pm 0.24
F5	200 \pm 3	2.93 \pm 0.04	8.6 \pm 0.4	0.26 \pm 0.03	99.53 \pm 0.39
F6	198 \pm 4	2.95 \pm 0.05	7.5 \pm 0.5	0.30 \pm 0.02	98.87 \pm 0.45
F7	200 \pm 4	2.94 \pm 0.04	7.8 \pm 0.5	0.20 \pm 0.01	99.93 \pm 0.73

* (Mean \pm SD)n=3, # n=6,\$ n=20

In vitro Dissolution study:

Table 12: Cumulative Percentage Drug Release of F1 to F7 Batches

Time(hr)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	10.9±0.12	12.9±0.22	10.3±0.11	7.4±0.12	9.2±0.11	7.6±0.13	6.2±0.10
1	23.8±0.23	14.2±0.28	10.9±0.21	9.3±0.23	10.9±0.25	12.5±0.19	7.8±0.14
2	32.0±0.34	20.5±0.37	15.3±0.23	18.8±0.24	27.6±0.28	26.2±0.24	13.4±0.19
3	49.9±0.51	41.3±0.38	38.4±0.27	32.2±0.29	39.4±0.30	40.0±0.30	18.4±0.21
4	54.0±0.60	54.9±0.39	49.6±0.35	47.4±0.34	56.02±0.36	44.0±0.35	27.0±0.26
5	73.2±0.61	69.0±0.43	67.2±0.39	57.6±0.38	70±0.39	65.3±0.40	32.0±0.31
6	76.3±0.62	78.1±0.48	67.4±0.41	63.6±0.42	73.4±0.42	76.2±0.51	36.0±0.33
7	86.1±0.63	81.2±0.49	76.9±0.49	69.1±0.49	80.5±0.41	80.0±0.58	38.0±0.37
8	90.2±0.68	90.0±0.54	86±0.52	70.2±0.50	80.7±0.48	80.6±0.61	39.0±0.39
9	92.4±0.75	92.8±0.63	94.1±0.62	70.6±0.62	80.9±0.51	82.2±0.62	41.8±0.41
10	92.1±0.79	95.0±0.71	96.1±0.69	78.9±0.69	88.8±0.60	83.0±0.75	43.2±0.45
11	99.2±0.88	99.0±0.85	98.2±0.72	94.2±0.72	96±0.73	93.6±0.82	44.4±0.50
12				96.6±0.82	99.2±0.85	96.0±0.89	45.8±0.57
13							44.0±0.59
14							56.4±0.62
15							74.4±0.65
16							75.6±0.68
17							79.4±0.71
18							80.0±0.74
19							88.2±0.77
20							96.8±0.81
21							97.2±0.82
22							97.8±0.83
23							98.8±0.85
24							99.9±0.88

Fig No: 4 Release Profiles of Glipizide Extended Release Formulations

(F1, F2, F3 , F4, F5, F6 and F7)

Fig No: 5 Time Vs Log Percent Drug Remaining Plots for Glipizide Extended Release Tablets (F1 - F4)

As observed from the percentage cumulative drug release, all the seven formulations studied are not able to provide an extended release of Glipizide up to 24hrs except in the case of F7 formulation. However the dissolution profile of innovator as described below when compared to F7 formulation showed similar release characteristics. The formulations F1, F2, F3, F4, F5 and F6 are unable to hold the drug during this initial period resulting in a drug release of 90-100 % within 12 hrs. This also resulted in poor f_2 values for these formulations. The formulation F7

shown similar dissolution compared with Innovator. The f_2 value of formulation F7 is 86 respectively. The F7 formulation is better fit in criteria. While formulation F1, F2, F3, F4, F5 and F6 showed quick drug release compared to the innovator. From above result of F1 to F7, it can be seen that concentration of HPMC and Ethyl Cellulose play a major factor in extending the release characteristics when given in combined optimized formulation there by modifying the release of Glipizide.

Fig No: 6 Log Time Vs Log Percent Released Plots for Glipizide Extended Release Tablets (F1 - F4)

Fig No:7 Log Time Vs Log Percent Released Plots for Glipizide Extended Release Tablets (F5 - F7)

Comparison of Formulation F8 with Marketed Product (Glynase- ER Tablets): The optimized formulations obtained in evaluation studies were compared with marketed formulation.

Table no. 13: Percentage Drug Release Profile of Formulation F8 Vs Marketed Product

Time(hr)	F7 Formulation	Marketed Formulation
0	0	0
0.5	6.2±0.10	6.0±0.16
1	7.8±0.14	8.1±0.17
2	13.4±0.19	13.0±0.19
3	18.4±0.21	16.5±0.21
4	27.0±0.26	26.3±0.22
5	32.0±0.31	31.5±0.26
6	36.0±0.33	33.6±0.29
7	38.0±0.37	35.1±0.32
8	39.0±0.39	37.0±0.36
9	41.8±0.41	39.6±0.38
10	43.2±0.45	41.5±0.40
11	44.4±0.50	45.8±0.46
12	45.8±0.57	47.5±0.51
13	48.0±0.59	49.0±0.59
14	56.4±0.62	51.2±0.61
15	74.4±0.65	55.1±0.65
16	75.6±0.68	65.6±0.67
17	79.4±0.71	70.2±0.69
18	80.0±0.74	78.2±0.70
19	88.2±0.77	81.7±0.79
20	96.8±0.81	87.4±0.80
21	97.2±0.82	92.9±0.81
22	97.8±0.83	95.5±0.85
23	98.8±0.85	97.2±0.87
24	99.9±0.88	100.2±0.89
Similarity Factor (<i>f</i>₂)		86.47

Fig No: 8 Comparison of Percentage Drug Release Profiles of Marketed Formulation & Optimized Formulation F7

The above study has shown that *In-Vitro* drug release profile and physical parameters of formulations F7 were found to be almost similar when compared to marketed product of Glucotrol- XL. Further Bio-Equivalence study followed by production scale can be undertaken if Bio-Equivalence study is passed through with positive results.

Drug Release Kinetics:

Table No: 14 Correlation Coefficient (R^2) Values in the Analysis of Release Data as per Zero order, First order, Higuchi, and Peppas Equation Models.

Batch No.	Zero Order		First Order		Higuchi	Korsmeyer Peppas	
	r^2	K_0 (h^{-1})	r^2	K_1 (h^{-1})	r^2	r^2	n value
F1	0.9245	8.7915	0.8807	0.3443	0.9784	0.9781	0.5741
F2	0.9424	9.3356	0.9154	0.3550	0.9605	0.9540	0.8674
F3	0.9603	9.5201	0.9208	0.3400	0.9506	0.9432	0.9896
F4	0.9578	7.8887	0.8498	0.2320	0.9589	0.9755	0.9147
F5	0.9215	8.1798	0.8457	0.3080	0.9675	0.9645	0.8339
F6	0.9216	8.0473	0.9422	0.2420	0.9616	0.9772	0.7494
F7	0.9769	4.1849	0.6954	0.2040	0.9250	0.9820	0.7750
Innovator	0.9746	4.5713	0.8603	0.0578	0.9679	0.9812	0.8927

Stability Study:**Table No: 15 Stability Study of F7 Formulation**

Test	Initial	40°C±2°C /75±5% RH		
		1 Month	2 Months	3 Months
Description	White, Round shaped Uncoated tablets, Plain Concave on both sides	Complies	Complies	Complies
Hardness (kg/cm²)	8.3±0.6	8.2±0.8	8.4±0.4	8.1±0.3
Thickness (mm)	2.92±0.06	2.90±0.06	2.91±0.06	2.90±0.06
Friability (%)	0.28	0.26	0.30	0.32
% Assay	99.86	98.26	98.30	97.80
% Drug Release				
8 Hr	36.0	35.4	33.1	34.1
16 Hr	76.8	74.6	78.3	75.4
24 Hr	99.9	99.6	99.5	99.5

The results of accelerated stability study reveals that the selected formulation of the Glipizide ER tablets are physically stable (passed all physico-technical parameters) with no significant change in appearance, hardness, thickness, and friability. The drug content and dissolution profile are also constant over the study period. Thus it can be concluded that a stable formulation of the Glipizide extended release Tablets can be formulated using above strategy.

CONCLUSION:

HPMC & Ethyl Cellulose are efficient as release retarding polymers for extended release tablets. Drug release from the prepared tablets was slowed over 24h and depended on the composition of HPMC & Ethyl Cellulose, Dicalcium phosphate. Glipizide release was diffusion controlled and follow zero order kinetics. Non-fickian diffusion was the drug release mechanism from the prepared Glipizide extended release tablets.

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